

IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF INTERACTIVE COMMUNICATION OF MASS-EDUCATIONAL EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6385169>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 14th March 2022

KEY WORDS

Higher education system, distance learning, development, interactive lessons, Information Communication Technology, the result of communication, interactive communication process.

ABSTRACT

Interactive communication can be carried out as live, synchronous, for example, in chats and in the form of delayed communication exchange participants' communication - in forums and e-mails. If the chat message is used as part of the main content, it becomes a synchronized connection. Thus, interactive methods can be considered as ways of organizing the interaction of teachers and students with each other and the interaction of all participants in the pedagogical process in order to create optimal conditions for development. In this article, opinions and comments are made about the improvement of the process of interactive communication of mass-educational education in higher educational institutions.

In order to ensure the continuity of the educational process in the higher educational institutions of the Republic, as well as to remotely methodically support the activities of obtaining knowledge of students, distance learning platforms were launched from April 1, 2020. Such platforms, first of all, gave students the opportunity to organize the learning process in a completely new format, that is, in a virtual environment. To do this, first of all, on the basis of Educational Directions and curricula of specialties, attention was paid to the creation of educational resources on the programs of the current semester subjects, the resources of distance learning from 6102 subjects taught in higher education were created and placed on the platforms of distance

learning of each higher educational institution. The work mentioned above gave students the opportunity to get distance education. To do this, the relevant educational resources have been created by professors and teachers in higher educational institutions, and they will be able to place on the platform all the educational materials that they have already prepared for their subjects. In order to improve performance in the Virtual environment, courses "technologies for the organization of distance learning" have been launched. Even in developed countries, initially distance learning was carried out mainly in the areas of laboratory work, where practical training was scarce.

The purpose of interactive interaction is to change, improve the models of behavior and activities of participants in the pedagogical process. The leading signs and means of interactive interaction, identified as a result of the analysis of interactive interaction practice, include dialogue, thinking activity, creation of meaning, sub-relations, selection earth, state of success, positive and optimism. evaluation, reasoning were considered. Interactive interaction is the process of joint activities of the teacher and students and its attributes are as follows:

- the spatial and temporal coexistence of the participants creates the possibility of personal communication between them;
- the presence of a common goal is the expected result of an activity that meets the interests of all and helps to meet the needs of everyone;
- planning, controlling, correcting and coordinating actions;
- division single process of cooperation, common activities between participants;;
- personality the emergence of relationships.

Interactive interaction is the intensive communicative activity of participants in the pedagogical process, the variety and change of types and forms, the method of activity. Spirituality is the process of conscious creation (creation) of a new content of the meaning of objects and phenomena of reality in the environment by the subjects of pedagogical interaction; expression of an individual attitude to events of Reality; Reflection from the point of view of individuality of the individual; understanding of the meaning of each participant in the pedagogical process, the

phenomenon, situation, the content of the pedagogical process becomes the product, the result of the formation of meaning by its participants.

Subjective relations - participants of pedagogical interaction (teacher and student) are subjects of the pedagogical process, i.e., they are the subjects of the pedagogical process. Its full-fledged participants, independent, creative, active, responsible; the subject of the student is determined mainly by the position of the subject of the teacher; each participant in the pedagogical process creates conditions for their development. Selection freedom- the ability of participants in the pedagogical process to consciously regulate and activate their behavior, pedagogical interactions that contribute to their optimal development, self-development; the ability of the individual to consciously regulate and activate their behavior; the need to overcome obstacles, difficulties; the ability of participants in the pedagogical process to act independently and interact with each other; conscious All the signs of this interactive interaction determine each other, the content and technological basis of the development of the teacher's subordination in professional education are united into a single set of attributes, which make up the desired component of this process.

Distance learning is a high-tech product of the scientific and technical revolution, widely applies the idea of a marketing approach in the provision of services to students, understanding its active distribution around the world. Today, Distance Learning includes computer and Internet learning technologies. The interaction of modern technologies is a connecting link between

participants, trainees and teachers, which can be divided into thousands of kilometers. The training is conducted in the corporate network, on the Internet, by e-mail and using other modern means of communication.

The structure of interactive pedagogical interaction is also the basis for the classification of active pedagogical methods. According to the leading function of a particular style in the organization of pedagogical interaction, the methods can be divided into the following groups:

- methods of creating a comfortable environment, organizing communication;
- methods of activity exchange;
- methods of thinking activity
- methods of creating meaning;
- reflective activity methods;
- integrated methods (interactive games).

Based on the legislation inherent in information, distance and communication educational technology, it was found that the formation and development of compartments among the participants of the interaction in the educational process occurs mainly as a result of the independent work of students with various types of educational weapons (electronic textbooks, electronic textbooks). Interactive educational programs, electronic knowledge base), in addition, in many respects in the use of communication networks (the Internet), which help to constantly enrich the experience of creative activity, formulate self-organization and self-realization mechanism.

Modular training includes the data of education, the content of training and the strict structure of the organization of

work of students with a complete, logically completed educational block (modules). The module deals with the subject of educational science. However, unlike the subject in the module, everything is measured, everything is evaluated: assignment, work, participation in classes, the initial, intermediate and final level of students. In the module, the educational objectives, tasks and learning levels of this module are clearly defined, skills and qualifications are named. In modular teaching, everything is pre-programmed: not only is the sequence of study of the teaching material, but also the degree of its mastering and control over the quality of assimilation.

In conclusion, in order to ensure the quality of distance education, both higher education institutions, professors and teachers, students and communication channels should be equally prepared. But from the beginning, the targeted activity aimed at introducing elements of distance learning into the field of education required the acceleration of these works due to the pandemic. The main thing is that the direction was set correctly, not being afraid to make mistakes in educational institutions, to a certain extent provided the beginning of the educational process in a new format. Interactive pedagogical interaction authoritarian-imperative is an alternative to traditional pedagogical interaction, which determines the essence of the pedagogical process alienated from the individual. The priority directions of interactive pedagogical interaction are such features as procedural, activity, communication, dialogue, the possibility of self-expression, the creation of meaning, reasoning, etc. Traditional pedagogical influence it is necessary to carry out a

compulsory program, to translate qualifications and skills of students.
knowledge and to formulate the

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